

Evaluation of Public Schools in Context of Learning Organization Characteristics

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Abstract

A learning organization is an environment where people constantly increase their capacity to create the results they really want, new ways of thinking are nurtured, shared dreams are freely discussed, and joint learning is constantly practiced. A learning school is not only a school where students actively participate in the teaching process, but also a school where students learn to learn as a process, an achievement. In the learning school, no distinction is made between the teacher and the student, the stakeholders at every level of the institution are the implementers and distributors of the learning process. School as a learning organization is an organization that "learns together", can control itself with a "cybernetic" approach, where creativity, change and continuity are the basic principles, and learning becomes a lifestyle. In this study, first of all, the concept of learning organization was defined, the characteristics of the learning organization were explained, the disciplines of learning organizations were summarized, and suggestions were developed by evaluating public schools in the context of learning organization characteristics.

Keywords: Learning organization, Learning school, Leader, Manager, Traditional organization

Kamu Okullarının Öğrenen Örgüt Özellikleri Açısından Değerlendirilmesi

Öz

Öğrenen örgüt, insanların gerçekten istedikleri sonuçları yaratmak için kapasitelerini sürekli artırdıkları, yeni düşünce yapılarının beslendiği, ortak hayallerin serbestçe tartışıldığı, beraberce öğrenmenin sürekli uygulandığı bir ortamdır. Öğrenen okul, öğrencilerin sadece öğretme sürecine aktif katılım sağladığı okul değil, öğrencilerin öğrenmeyi bir süreç, bir kazanım olarak öğrendikleri okuldur. Öğrenen okulda, öğretmen ve öğrenci ayrımı yapılmaz, kurumun her kademesinde bulunan paydaşlar, öğrenme sürecinin uygulayıcısı ve dağıtıcısıdır. Öğrenen örgüt olarak okul, "birlikte öğrenen", "sibernetik" yaklaşımla kendini denetleyebilen, yaratıcılığın, değişimin ve sürekliliğin temel ilke olduğu, öğrenmenin yaşam tarzı haline geldiği örgütlerdir. Bu çalışmada öncelikle öğrenen örgüt kavramı tanımlanmış, öğrenen örgütün özellikleri açıklanmış, öğrenen örgütlerin sahip olduğu disiplinler özetlenmiş ve öğrenen örgüt özellikleri bağlamında kamu okulları değerlendirilerek öneriler geliştirilmiştir.

Anahtar Sözcükler: Öğrenen örgüt, Öğrenen okul, Lider, Yönetici, Geleneksel örgüt

Type: Research article	Sending Date: 18.12.2022	Acceptance Date: 01.03.2023
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To cite: Özbay, T., Uzunlar, Ö.F., Demir, H., Yener, A., Baştuğ, H., Kıratlı-Baştuğ, B., & Ergin, Y. (2023). Evaluation of public schools in context of learning organization characteristics. *Journal of Unique Glance at Education*, 1(1), 30-43. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7575597

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Instroduction

Each era had a premise value; Philosophy in Antiquity, Religion in the Middle Ages, New Science in the Age. Today's most important value is technology and therefore knowledge. Another factor that is as effective as the individual in acquiring, developing and transferring information is are organizations. In this ever-changing age, reaching information, catching innovation, learning the transformation of organizations is inevitable in order to ensure its continuity. learning, human, learning organizations based on knowledge, quality and human values should be brought to the fore (Çalık, 2003). Learning organizations are organizations that put the individual in the center and are active in competition. As a means of creating positive synergy by increasing quality on the basis of learning and qualifications. Transformative, modern, which uses learning and strives to make learning a permanent culture and open systems. Schools, which are the first step of formal learning, are in this context is of great importance.

In the information society, schools that are educational organizations are not teaching institutions but learning institutions (Taşargöl, 2013). The existence of schools in the contemporary education environment Its sustainability depends on the successful realization of this transformation. learning school, in which students are active, learning activity is at the forefront, not teaching activity is the school where he attended (Fındıkçı, 1996). It teaches students to access information, an education system that makes them autonomous learners, but schools are learning organizations become possible.

Depending on the pace of social and educational change, the necessity of schools to be "learning organizations" is becoming increasingly important. As a learning organization, the staff of the school should see their professional development not as a task to be completed but as an ongoing job of a lifelong learner. The main goal in such an institution is to focus on student learning. In creating a learning school that will provide individual and collective learning, the leader has an important role, especially in creating the right culture and climate. It is impossible to create a learning school without such dedication.

Learning Organization Concept

In today's rapidly changing and developing world, it is not enough to have a thinker for the organization. The thought of one person thinking of everything from above and others following him loses its importance and value. Therefore, the need for the organization to learn as a whole arises. The rapidly changing management understandings in the world cause the restructuring of organizations and the emergence of new trends. One of these trends is the concept of "learning organization". In addition to these explanations, the fact that organizations have become "learning organizations" is basically the result of a development according to some authors. According to these authors, "learning organization" refers to the last step in this development process (Koçel, 2005; Özgen & Türk, 1996)

According to the philosophy of the learning organization, the way to adapt to changing conditions is through continuous learning. The learning process is also defined as the assimilation of experiences, increasing the capacity of people to develop new ideas and find solutions to problems (Özgen & Türk, 1996; Taşkın, 1993). Because education, which is considered as a factor of production, no matter how important it is, if employees and organizations do not learn from it and apply it, it will not work.

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The learning organization is where people continually increase their capacity to create the results they really want; new mindsets are nurtured; where common dreams are freely discussed; It is an environment where collaborative learning is practiced continuously. The Learning Organization, with its problem-solving-based structure, is designed for effectiveness differs from the traditional organization (Akhtar ve Khan, 2011). Other learning organization it is the spread of “learning” activity to all parts of the business that differentiates it from other organizations for learning. Instead of specifying a separate time frame, it is possible to interact with individuals in the organization (collaboration, division of labor) learning turns into a process (Braham, 1998). When learning organizations are mentioned, organizations that can predict change and adapt quickly to change come to mind. Garvin (2000) learner organizations; defines them as structures that produce and interpret information, use new information and transform it into behavior.

In summary, a learning organization is one in which people continually increase their capacity to create the results they truly want; new mindsets are nurtured; where common dreams are freely discussed; It is an environment where collaborative learning is practiced continuously. There is a constant cultural change in this environment. In order to create this environment, change agents who believe in this approach are needed and the support of the top management is inevitable for success. However, in such an environment, learning organizations can constantly renew themselves and maintain their dynamism (Kaplama & Varoğlu, 1997).

Disciplines of the Learning Organization

The learning organization consists of learning and mastering the five 'learning disciplines' (Senge, 2007). Each discipline must be studied individually, but all together can make up the learning organization. These:

Personal Dominance: The individual's self-education and the necessary competence form the basis of organizational learning. Personal competence is the discipline of constantly opening and deepening our personal vision, focusing our energies and seeing reality objectively. Individuals' personal abilities cost the organization they are in. The personal abilities gathered under the umbrella of an organization are defined as the knowledge and learning capacity of that organization. Therefore, an organization's willingness and capacity to learn cannot be greater than that of its members. Personal mastery is when individuals within the organization learn to develop their own personal capacity to achieve the results they desire. In other words, personal mastery requires creating appropriate learning environments that will enable teammates' organizational learning in line with the desired organizational goals and objectives.

The individual needs to clarify his or her vision and become adept at helping to create an organization that supports its employees in developing their individual skills. Developing an individual vision is the foundation of a shared vision. Individuals must be able to organize their own lives according to what is important to them. A truly shared vision can only be developed when individuals in the organization can receive support for their desire to improve themselves.

Mental Models: Mental models include the enrichment of each individual's inner world, understanding how his personal decisions and actions are shaped, and constantly pondering enlightenment. Therefore, mental models; It is a system of values that directs individual and social preferences and behaviors, shapes social attitudes, rooted in prejudices or does not allow them to pass. It is to create new ways of thinking and analysis methods belonging to the person

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and in this way to make himself more open to the influences and suggestions from others. Mental models help us both re-make sense of the world and guide our actions.

Shared Vision: Vision is a perspective formed by understanding, views and thoughts that express where and under what conditions an organization will be for the future. The idea of shared vision includes the principles that support the journey to the future and guide the practices, as well as the strengthening of the sense of belonging of the individuals within a certain group and the creation of a common desire for the future.

Team Learning: As a basic concept, team learning depends on the production of institutional knowledge. Teams can be seen as non-individual basic learning units. The discipline of team learning involves uncovering a talent greater than the sum of the abilities of individual individuals and developing the relational thinking styles and capacities of groups within the organization. In order to be able to see and interpret information objectively, it is necessary to be able to examine, discuss and interpret it by a certain group. In addition, the purpose of team learning in organizations is to realize an effective synergy. Revealing a shared picture of the future in terms of individuals and organizations makes it possible for all members of the organization to unite around common beliefs and values, to devote themselves to the organization and to participate in activities. The discipline of team learning begins with “dialogue”; it is the capacity of members of a team to set aside assumptions and engage in genuine "thinking together".

Systems Thinking: Systems thinking encompasses the language and ways of thinking necessary to understand and describe the interrelationships and pressure groups that shape organizational behavior. This discipline helps employees and managers understand how systems will change more effectively and act in harmony with the processes of the wider natural and economic environment. Looking at the organization from the perspective of the system envisages first identifying its internal and external stakeholders, then recognizing the system in general and optimizing it. In other words, organizations that do not have systems thinking have to take two steps forward and one step back. We can liken the organization and its employees to a system connected by an invisible fabric of interrelated actions. Systems thinking is a conceptual framework, a body of knowledge and tools. It allows us to see the whole plot more clearly and helps us see how we can change them most effectively. Systems thinking is the development of the ability to see existing but invisible connections between activities that are related to each other and to understand the effects they have on each other. With this aspect, systems thinking is the structure that gathers learning organization disciplines.

Characteristics of Learning Organizations

The five basic principles of the learning organization, which was first used by Senge as a concept learning discipline: Systems thinking, personal mastery, mental models, shared vision and team learning (Çalık, 2003; Gürkan 2007; Senge, 2007). System the idea of seeing the plot as a whole and how it can be changed necessary to understand. The discipline of personal dominance is the individual truth evaluation, deepening and assimilation of thought. Mental models are it is the assumptions, beliefs and perspectives that shape the perception of the world vision group. It is a joint plan for the future. Learning in a team is as a joint action of the members of the organization with the idea of “unity” away from individuality imaginable.

The feature that makes learning organizations different from other organizations is that the learning process decisiveness and continuity of the interaction between all stakeholders of

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the organization, spread to every layer that is the fact. Here, learning is not a finite and time-constrained concept; organization retrospective evaluations carried out simultaneously with the development of its members and the problematic of “what” should be done about the future, including the dimension of “how” should be done, it is a moving process in which everyone is active at some point in the change. Traditional in organizations, the vision is determined by the management or manager, while in learning organizations vision, active participants who go beyond the stakeholders' own areas of responsibility, it comes out of a common consciousness with what they have become. This is the ability to achieve goals within the organization it brings a more realistic approach at its point.

The problem in traditional organizations solving, often through authority and power as an extension of the hierarchical structure while taking place, work through the evaluation of past experiences in learning organizations it is the process of developing solutions within the union. Responsibilities and roles, each of the organization it is distributed among each member at its level; everyone is involved in the success/failure of the organization he is influential and has a say in its development/regression. Leaders in learning organizations, autocratic and it is not the most authoritative, but rather distributive and democratic. Leaders of learning organizations they are involved in the process through interaction and intervention in planning; the members themselves in shaping the future of the organization and the system by enabling it to realize they are supporters.

Organizational learning types can be classified in many different ways. In general on the other hand, first, when employees encounter a problem from the external environment with the objectives of the current strategy with a problem-solving-oriented approach and without any change in vision, the event is simply a change of behavior and from the "one-way learning" process, which is the solution of can be mentioned. In this process, existing norms and values are not questioned they stay in line with their determined targets (Yazıcı, 2001). As a second process “Double-loop learning” is the questioning of the values and methods of the organization, to be detected and corrected. Here, the formation/change of organizational culture there is an opportunity to encourage employees to learn new things. As the third In the "cybernetic" learning approach, there is a continuous interaction and information with the system environment is in the exchange; so that the system is intelligent and self-regulating (Çalık, 2003). Organizational learning types, “from mistakes” learning”, evaluation of organizational problems in the past, “learning from customers” means people who are directly involved in the product/output assessments, “learning by benchmarking”, valuation of practices carried out by other institutions/organizations for better and its adaptation, “learning to learn together” means that the members at all levels learning by working through common consciousness through interaction and sharing can be classified.

The vision of traditional organizations is determined by the top management. In learning organizations, on the other hand, there is a shared vision that emerges from all organizational units. However, senior management is responsible for ensuring the emergence and development of the vision. In the classical organization, while the top management decides what to do, individuals and units in the organization are given the task of continuing their actions in this direction (Tolgay, 2010).

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Table 1. *Comparison of Learning Organizations and Traditional Organizations*

Learning Features	Traditional Organizations	Learning Organizations
who is learning	Posted, rewarded or similar groups (managers, other organization members)	Everyone, all employees, all department members
who teaches	In-house trainer or external experts	People closest to the job, educators, experts.
Who is responsible	education department	Everybody
What kind of learning tools do people use?	Lessons, training on the job. Master-apprentice relationship, formal education, learning plans.	Lectures, on-the-job training, learning plans, benchmarks, teams, personal efforts, pair work.
When employees learn	When they have to, the first few months, when they have to	Always long term.
What skills do employees learn	Technical	Technical, commercial, interpersonal, learn to learn
Where do they learn	In classrooms, at work	In classrooms, in meetings, in the workplace and outside
Timing	today's requirements	future requirements
Feelings	without enthusiasm	Enthusiastic

Organizational theorists consider the learning organization as a solution to the three basic problems that exist in traditional organizational structures: segmentation, competition, and responsiveness. First, segmentation, which is based on specialization in learning organizations, prioritizes flexibility by presenting it as different functions that enable autonomous movement. Second, learning organizations place emphasis on cooperation as well as competition. Overemphasis on competition can weaken cooperation. Members of the management team compete with each other to demonstrate that they are fairer, more knowledgeable, and persuasive. The third is reaction in traditional organizations (Kingır & Mesci, 2007).

School as a Learning Organization

In the information society, the purpose of education today, the presentation of information and where desired it's not a recall. The education system will be able to realize autonomous learning demands the development of individuals. For this purpose, schools are also organizationally must learn to learn. The learning school is active in the teaching process of the students not the school in which they participate, but rather the students' learning as a process, an achievement it's the school where he learns. In the learning school, there is no distinction between teacher and student; each of the institution stakeholders at the level of education are the implementers and distributors of the learning process. As a learning organization, the school establishes itself with a "co-learning", "cybernetic" approach control, creativity, change and continuity are the basic principles, learning organizations that have become a lifestyle (Aksu, 2013; Subaş, 2010). Başaran, learning states the characteristics of schools as organizations as follows (Taşargöl, 2013):

1. Defines expected learning with clearly stated objectives and is visionary.
2. It creates a culture of change.
3. The staff tends to develop and supports its staff.
4. Performs the right service in the process of social change.
5. Collaborates with different groups and renews the organizational structure.
6. Constantly correcting himself by getting feedback from the production process and its outputs tries to renew it.

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In this context, first of all, it is necessary to examine the development of vision. In learning organizations, the vision is determined not only by the manager but also by the organization at all levels determined by the joint participation of its members. In this way, the validity of the vision realism and renewal may be possible. Schools to learning organizations one of the most important factors in the transformation of the culture is the culture of change. Creating a culture of change begins with the assimilation of the concept of change. It, will begin with the question of “what” is the thing that needs to change, parties (students, teachers, administrators, parents, school staff) agree on this issue. will evolve into the process by asking the question of "how" what problems can be encountered and what the solutions can be process will be expanded. However, it should not be forgotten that change is a long and it is a complicated process; continuously to achieve the goals set in the vision. students and students with a high desire for learning and development in an individual sense and renewing strategies needs teachers. In maintaining this delicate balance of change, personnel development is one of the key issues.

First of all, the school administrator's democratic, supporting, respectful to all groups and playing a conciliatory role in school-environment relations must. Thus, in-service training in schools and out of school teacher participation in activities will increase, their professional development will be supported and the teacher, who knows that he is important, will perform the right services in the change process. As a learning organization, the school's ability to cooperate with different groups to ensure the openness of the process and to include educational technologies in the learning process can be accomplished by communication with other institutions will increase the quality of the organization, two-way interaction strengthens ties with society and helps to follow innovations will become an element. Getting feedback from processes and outputs and system improvement in the context of this, successful teachers and students are motivated by rewarding, right/wrong in operation can be made visible to everyone.

The role of administrators in schools as a learning organization, vision goals and school culture, increasing the competence of employees, cooperation and dissemination of sharing. For this, first of all, managers open to criticism, new ideas and approaches, supporting the development of teachers, they must prove to be democratic and collaborative leaders. Opportunity throughout the school and it should create equality of opportunity for all stakeholders and spread the importance of learning as its mission they should acquire. Curriculum, wishes and needs of teachers, students and parents converted into a common denominator accordingly. In the learning school, teachers only transferring information, memorizing, evoking is not here, teaching here, multidimensionality wins. The teacher is the one who teaches the students to search, question and acquire knowledge; at the same time more than his colleagues, superiors, subordinates and all. He is a learner from the student and even with the student. The teacher is now the informant not in a position, but in a position of learning while teaching (Özdemir, 2000). Focus in this new system, where the student is the point, knowledge is now used and more it is an “acquired” resource for production. As a learning organization, the school gives them the ability to manage themselves; their desire and enthusiasm for learning encouraged students internalize learning and make it a part of their lives they have brought.

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Learning Organizations and Leadership

Leadership has an important meaning for learning organizations. Because, leaders in learning organizations are people who walk forward, reveal the learning abilities and competencies of the organization, and build learning organizations by removing the obstacles to organizational learning, regardless of their positions in the management or hierarchical authority. Senge (2007) state that leaders who think, question and take risks can create and develop a learning organizational culture. Avalio and Bass (2002) identified three basic leadership types as transformational, follow-up and ineffective (laissez-faire) leadership and defined the roles of these leadership styles on organizational success and effectiveness.

To increase the capacity of schools to be learning organizations; It is important to allow individuals with creative thinking skills to work in an environment where they can easily explain their thoughts and to provide a suitable environment for them to implement these ideas. Educational administrators who exhibit authoritarian or ineffective leadership styles cause teachers with creative thinking skills to distance themselves from the organization or to withdraw into themselves (Uzunçarşılı & Özdayı, 1997). School administrators should determine their own mental models and be the pioneers of creating an environment that is open to change and conducive to learning (Schlechty, 2009).

Senge mentions four competencies as the leadership role of the learning organization. First, leaders need to be mobilized and have difficulties with no easy solutions the ability to lead people to problems. Second, the leader's difficult the need to recognize systems thinking when dealing with situations. As the third, the leader must also be the leader of learning. Reflecting on your own decisions and those of others they know that it takes time to capitalize on their ideas leaders he is also aware of his own personal visions, strengths and weaknesses.

To be a living organization that constantly learns, first of all, It means that the leader is always open to new learnings. Also, employees some behavioral models of leaders to reveal their learning abilities display is important. To create an organizational environment that is willing to learn continuously, to create effective creative ideas and to disseminate these ideas within the organization and development are examples of these behavioral patterns learner. Leaders have four basic roles in organizations (Yazıcı, 2001):

1. Leaders, primarily with their thoughts and behaviors, they should show that they are people who are open to learning and development and they should take an active role in all kinds of activities. However, by this the attitudes and behaviors of the employees of the organization as a result of an interaction can be directed.
2. Presenting learning and development opportunities to all employees of the organization should take on the role of support and support.
3. By integrating learning opportunities into their daily work, they should create a system where they can find the opportunity to learn at any time.
4. Importance of learning to other departments and the organization as a whole should undertake the dissemination mission.

To transform their schools into lifelong learning, by making them work towards their goals and enabling them to be innovative the primary responsibility for implementing organizational learning disciplines rests with school leaders decreases. According to Senge, “organizational learning” is a possibility, that is, its own future a possibility that provides the

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capacity to create. School leadership, suitable for a situation multiple perspectives, choosing the structure or a combination of structures unlocks this capacity. Establishing organizational learning and particularly adept at using symbolic structure to convey organizational vision.

Learning School Manager

In the information society, the aim of education today is not the presentation of information and its recall when requested. The education system demands the training of individuals who can realize autonomous learning. For this purpose, schools also need to learn to learn organizationally. A learning school is not a school where students actively participate in the teaching process, but a school where students learn to learn as a process, an achievement. In the learning school, there is no distinction between teacher and student; Stakeholders at all levels of the institution are the implementers and distributors of the learning process. School as a learning organization is an organization that "learns together", can control itself with a "cybernetic" approach, where creativity, change and continuity are the basic principles, and learning becomes a lifestyle.

The best way to ensure that effective ideas are accepted within the organization is to spread it throughout the organization. For this, first of all, there must be a vision and understanding patterns shared by the employees within the organization. The existence of such a culture ensures the volunteering of the employees, increasing the competencies and learning capacities of the employees; moving from approaches that punish mistakes to approaches that take lessons from mistakes and removing all obstacles for change to happen; The openness of employees to each other will ensure that effective ideas are easily spread within the organization and generalized by being accepted within the framework of a common understanding and broad-mindedness.

In learning organizations, the vision should be determined not only by the manager but also by the joint participation of the members of the organization at all levels. In this way, the validity of the vision, its realism in achieving the goals and its renewal can be possible. Another important factor in transforming schools into learning organizations is the culture of change. Creating a culture of change begins with the assimilation of the concept of change. This will begin with the question of "what" is the thing that needs to change, and the process will evolve by asking the question "how" after the parties (student, teachers, administrators, parents, school staff) agree on this issue. The process will be expanded by discussing what the solutions might be.

First of all, the school administrator should assume the role of democratic, supportive, respectful to all groups and conciliatory in school-environment relations. In this way, teacher participation in in-service training activities held in schools and outside the school will increase, and the teacher, who knows that his professional development is supported and cared for, will provide the right services in the change process. The school's ability to cooperate with different groups as a learning organization can be achieved by providing the openness of the learning process and incorporating educational technologies into the learning process. Communication with other institutions will increase the quality of the organization, two-way interaction will strengthen ties with the society and become a helpful element in following the innovations. In the context of receiving feedback from the process and its outputs and system improvement, successful teachers and students can be motivated by rewarding, and the right/wrong things in the process can be made visible to everyone.

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The role of administrators in schools as a learning organization is to adopt the vision goals and school culture, to increase the competencies of the employees, and to expand cooperation and sharing. For this, first of all, administrators must prove to their employees that they are democratic and sharing leaders who are open to criticism, new thoughts and approaches, support the development of teachers. They should create equality of opportunity and opportunity for all stakeholders throughout the school and make it their mission to spread the importance of learning.

To increase the capacity of schools to be learning organizations; It is important to allow individuals with creative thinking skills to work in an environment where they can easily explain their thoughts and to provide a suitable environment for them to implement these ideas. Educational administrators who exhibit authoritarian or ineffective leadership styles cause teachers with creative thinking skills to distance themselves from the organization or to withdraw into themselves. School administrators should determine their own mental models and be the pioneers of creating an environment open to change and conducive to learning.

The best manager is one who creates a healthy and strong learning environment and constantly encourages the self-cultivation of everyone in the organization; In addition, working with qualified individuals does not eliminate the need for continuous learning of those individuals. The learning organization requires a new understanding of leadership. Defining the mission of the organization requires expressing this vision to the employees of the organization by creating a sense of shared goals that binds together the various activities done throughout the organization as a whole.

Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendations

The most important feature of the century we live in is the rapid changes. Especially in the last 20-25 years, the developments and changes in the field of communication have caused radical changes on organizations, and the use of information systems based on information technologies has begun in a wide area from the public to the private sector. The use of information systems has changed the current life styles of individuals and societies, as well as different effects on organizational structures, ways of doing business, and relations between individuals working in the organization. The desire to make full use of information technologies for organizational purposes has revealed the necessity of integrating and managing these technologies within a system framework. Accordingly, information processing units have been established in most organizations (Karahan & Yılmaz, 2010).

The world has now entered the age of the "information society". Not only individuals and states, but also companies have entered into an intense learning need. In the face of the fierce competition environment, rapid change in science and technology, and environmental conditions that are increasingly uncertain and complex, organizations have entered into new searches. In the context of these quests, organizations are increasingly trying to become a "learning organization" (Öneren, 2008).

The fact that a dynamic and proactive continuous education model designed within a system approach that accurately expresses today's conditions in organizations has become operational is of great importance in terms of training and development activities on the one hand, and creating a learning organization on the other. A learning organization consists of learning individuals. Continuing education is an approach that enables employees in the organization to become learning individuals. Thanks to continuous education, continuous

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learning will result in making education a lifestyle by employees, and employees who have adopted learning as a lifestyle will start learning as a group with collective learning (Atak & Atik, 2007).

Learning organizations, with their structures that require constant change, development and learning, are key to individual and organizational development with behaviors such as providing economic returns for the business, positive feelings of employees, sensitivity to the wishes and needs of employees, and solving problems and conflicts (İmamoğlu & Mutlu, 2012).

It should not be forgotten that the basis of learning organizations is human; A person who is open to learning, a person who follows change and can contribute to change. As we mentioned earlier, learning is one of the few advantages that exist today to compete better. This brings some responsibilities to institutions and their employees. Institutions should make some investments in order to be a learning organization and the learning event should be organized in a way that covers everyone. Learning organizations have some characteristics. In order to be a learning organization, these features must be taken into account and fulfilled one by one by the institution that wants to be a learning organization. In this sense, in order to be a learning organization, it is necessary to respond to the learning needs of the employees, to create a suitable learning environment, to see and eliminate the learning deficiencies, to consider the learning organization disciplines as a whole, to allocate the necessary resources and to provide opportunities to encourage the employees in this regard (Çoban, 2006).

Education in the information age, keeping up with the speed of developments, being able to follow up-to-date it has gained a life-long feature due to reasons such as: In such a case, teaching learning activities also change shape, the structure of educational organizations and their stakeholders must change radically. Today, schools are becoming learning organizations. It seems like the only way they can survive change, labor, time, it is a process that requires investment and cooperation. States first, starting from the top, review their policies and strategies to make schools learning organizations should pass. Afterwards, educational environments, administrators and teachers are learning schools. Professional development to be organized to improve the perceptions of should be improved through seminars, workshops and committees. Monitored in teacher training the way should be modernized, it should be an opportunity for teachers to acquire a culture of self-development should be given. As regulars of lifelong learning, teachers use technology and must constantly follow the innovations in education in the global sense, should make the temperament of their relationships collaborative and ultimately teach their students to learn. As teachers, they should set an example. Autonomous learning individuals, learning schools; learning schools evolve into a system with high functionality; the system itself it serves for the construction of an organic and learning world that is self-sufficient.

Every individual working in a learning organization should think together with his teammates in line with the purpose of the business, provide competitive advantages in order to be successful, and take his place by taking important steps in our changing world. At the same time, the models specified in learning organizations should be well learned, applied, supported and addressed by all members of the group within the framework of systems theory. Considering the free market economy, companies have made significant contributions to creativity, openness, group work and continuous self-improvement instead of complexity by using learning organizations. Even if the specified conditions are met in the learning

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organization, the absence of a leader to guide the group can create a significant deficiency. Considering the mistakes made in the past, generating new ideas should be among the important issues. The "five disciplines" developed by Senge can be used by learning organizations in studies (Kıngır & Mesci, 2007).

In recent times, where international competition has accelerated, the rapid pace of integration with the World these developments have forced organizations to keep up with these rapid developments. These rapid developments have left organizations faced with very different and new problems. While struggling with these, employees should learn to learn both individually and as a team, while organizations should be planned and flexible and closely follow global developments. Sharing information with all employees will only be possible with the understanding of a learning organization. In order to be successful and gain competitive advantage, organizations should be learning organizations that take organizational learning into account today and in the future (Öneren, 2008).

In the studies to be carried out on the way to become a learning organization, the point of view of the institution manager is very important. The organization will develop continuously with managers who are open to innovations, can make correct and constructive criticisms, evaluate the criticisms without prejudice and ensure their personal development. The manager, who is not the manager but the person consulted, will be in constant communication with his employees. It will deal with the entire organization in any work done. Since the authoritarian management approach is replaced by a flexible management approach, employees will not have to comply with strict rules. Employees who feel that they are valued will increase their productivity. Studies in learning organizations should cover a long period of time. Because the studies complement each other.

It is not considered possible for our schools to be evaluated as learning organizations with their current status. It can be said that our schools often show traditional organizational characteristics. Strict hierarchy, excessive adherence to rules, test anxiety, ranking and classification, strict superior-subordinate relationship are some examples of these. Specialization, autonomous training, flexible working, cooperation and trust are essential in learning organizations. In learning organizations, the wishes and needs of individuals as well as the goals of the organization are taken into account, and the leadership understanding that strives to carry the followers forward is displayed in these organizations. When the subject is evaluated in this context, it can be said that our schools do not fully have the characteristics of a learning organization.

He who has not learned to learn himself cannot give the ability to learn to anyone else. In this respect, it is imperative that schools be learning and developing organizations. Being a learning organization will be possible by being a learner as an organization and being an organization that can organize learning. Organizational learning is a dynamic concept that expresses a change and development, especially structural. A learning school refers to a learning institution as an organization. Being a learning school is possible with the cooperation of its members. Such learning is a process in which school members continuously improve their qualifications, but it is also a process that improves the learning capacity and experience of the learning school. Being a learning school means aiming to improve school quality according to changing needs and conditions. For this, a serious change and transformation process should be started from the curricula to the educational philosophy and policies. Schools should be structured flexibly, exam anxiety should be eliminated, rigid hierarchy should be set aside,

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excessive prescriptiveness should be abandoned, people should be valued, employees' participation in the decisions taken should be ensured, a democratic school environment should be established, and a good school climate should be established. In order for schools to maintain their continuity and become a learning organization, the management staff must be open-minded, supportive of education and development, and open to innovations.

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Ethical Declaration and Committee Approval

In this research, the principles of scientific research and publication ethics were followed. This study does not require ethics committee approval. Because this study; It is not a study that collects data from the participants by using survey, interview, focus group work, observation, experiment, interview techniques. This study is not a study in which humans and animals are used for experimental or other scientific purposes. This study is not a clinical study on humans or animals.